

Recent Issues and Challenges of Indian Society and Role of Humanities

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Abstract

The Fifth Industrial Revolution will see the transformation of the manufacturing sector that can ignite the industrial revolution. Fifth Industrial revolution should ideally be the evolution of the modern manufacturing process in order to allow man and machine to perform work hand-in-hand, combining the unique, cognitive abilities of workers and the accurate, technical expertise of robots to bring in an innovative culture into the workforce. The fifth-generation industry brings customer satisfaction and opens a new market. Fifth Industrial revolution is going to be distinguished by the collaboration between machines and human beings, with the ultimate objective to provide additional value to production, by creating customized products able to satisfy consumers' requirements. The following research paper aims at defining how there are some issues and challenges that not only India but the whole world is facing. The issues which affect the man and woman and their psychology, their status in the society, different nations and their changing policies, etc. the present paper also throws light on how different issues are interrelated with each other. If these issues are not treated very well then it will show very deep impact on the future generations and their health hygiene, physical, mental abilities. The present paper also tries to discuss the possible ways to resolve the issues and challenges and to settle future of next generations.

Introduction

The twentieth century gave us a lot of things which made our life easier and fuller of comfort. Every invention came with its drawbacks. Most of time human failed to understand them. Researchers are engaged in increasing the life span of human with different medicines. Parallel we overcome so many diseases that also help to increase the human population. Now it becomes difficult task to feed them. Increase in population gave

rise to so many problems like hunger, lack of basic needs, health issues, societal problems international politics, relation between different nations etc.

We all know the future is not necessarily too easy. If current trends in population growth, resource depletion, climate change, terrorism, organized crime, and disease continue and converge over the next 5 to 10 decades, it is easy to imagine a continually unstable world with a series of unimaginable results. At the same time, if current trends in self-organization via future Internets, transnational cooperation, materials science, 3-D printing, alternative energy, cognitive science, inter-religious dialogues, synthetic biology, and nanotechnology continue and converge over the next 5 to 10 decades, it is easy to imagine a world that works for all.

Computational biophysics can enforce the physical forces among atoms, making medical diagnostics and treatment more accurate. It can create computer matching programmes to quickly reduce the number of possible cures for specific diseases, with millions of people donating their unused computer capacity to run the matching programmes. Computer engineering brings together the world's available information and computer models to rapidly accelerate efficiencies in design. The world is getting richer, healthier, better educated, more peaceful, and better connected and people are living longer, yet half the world is potentially unstable. Protesters around the world show a growing unwillingness to tolerate unethical decision-making by power elites. An increasingly educated and Internet-connected generation is rising up against the abuse of power. Food prices are rising, water tables are falling, corruption and organized crime are increasing, environmental viability for our life support is diminishing, debt and economic insecurity are increasing, climate change continues, and the gap between the rich and poor continues to widen dangerously.

History has taught us that good ideas and technologies can have unintended and negative consequences. These capabilities will eventually make it possible for a single individual acting alone to make and deploy a bio-weapon of mass destruction and for organized crime to become far more powerful than today — when its combined income is already twice that of the total of the world's military budgets. These and other dangerous future possibilities are not inevitable; there are many excellent solutions being pursued and making great progress, unbeknownst to the general public

Farmers all over the world are plagued by several issues. These problems indirectly and directly affect the farmer's life. Furthermore, farming practices and other aspects of agriculture can take up resources and time. The problems faced by farmers are typically unnoticed in the food industry. The problems like,

1. Inadequate transport

Farmers in developing countries have a hard time transporting their produce to markets due to lack of roads, vehicles and money. They often have to carry their produce from the farm to local markets on foot or by bicycle, which can be challenging and time-consuming. This means that they often have to sell their produce at very low prices because they cannot transport it to places where there is better demand for food.

2. Lack of capital

Farmers need capital to get their businesses off the ground and grow them into successful operations. However, they often have little access to credit or financing because lenders don't understand their unique needs. The lack of financial resources affects not only productivity but also affects the quality of agricultural produce. Farmers in some developing countries do not have access to adequate funds to invest in better technologies, machinery and equipment which results in poor-quality agricultural produce.

3. Agricultural marketing

Agricultural marketing refers to the process of bringing a product from the farmer to the consumer. It includes activities such as finding buyers for the products, negotiating prices, transporting goods and getting feedback on quality. Because there are many people involved in this process, it can be quite challenging. Farmers have to find buyers who will pay them a fair price for their goods while also ensuring that they don't sell too cheap or too expensively.

In many cases, they are forced to sell their products at a low price or even give them away because they cannot find buyers. This situation creates an incentive for small farmers not to produce more than what they need for their own consumption.

4. Soil erosion

Soil erosion is a natural process that happens when wind or water moves soil particles from one place to another. When this happens on a large scale, it causes serious problems for farmers.

Soil erosion is caused by many factors including over-tillage of the soil, which erodes soil quality and retains less water. When it floods, it removes the top layers of soil very quickly. Soil erosion can be prevented by controlling the amount of water used for irrigation, using mulch and cover crops to protect soil from wind and water erosion, and preventing overgrazing by livestock.

5. Irrigation problems

Irrigation is known to help improve agricultural production, and while irrigation methods have improved to help increase the income of farmers, there are still numerous irrigation-related hurdles that make it harder for farmers to get income commensurate to their expenditure.

Whether it's because of droughts, floods, or just low rainfall, irrigation can be difficult to maintain. Farmers have often been forced to fall back on groundwater resources when surface water sources dry up during droughts.

6. Lack of high-quality seeds

The quality of seed used in farming is essential in attaining a higher crop yield. It is also important in getting sustained growth in agricultural production. Distribution of high-quality seed is as important as seed production. High-quality seeds are typically out of reach for most farmers, especially marginal and small farmers due to their prohibitively high prices.

7. Lack of infrastructure in the agriculture sector

One of the biggest issues that farmers face is lack of infrastructure. This includes poor roads, transportation facilities and so on. Farmers have to depend on others for transport services which increase their costs significantly. Without proper transportation facilities, it becomes difficult for farmers to sell their produce at reasonable prices within their respective localities or even outside their villages or townships.

8. Biocides and fertilizers

Biocides are used in the form of pesticides to kill insects and other pests that destroy crops. However, they can also have harmful effects on humans and animals who eat food that has been treated with them. This may result in health problems such as cancer or infertility. Biocides are also linked to water pollution because they can be washed into rivers or lakes by rainwater after application onto crops.

9. Lack of modern farming equipment

One of the major problems faced by farmers is the lack of adequate farm equipment which can hamper their ability to adapt to the requirements of modern farming practices. When farmers are trained using the equipment, their lives can significantly develop. Implementation of said equipment is important.

When evaluating environmental impact, experts use two types of indicators: "means-based", which is based on the farmer's production methods, and "effect-based", which is the impact that farming methods have on the farming system or on emissions to the environment. An example of a means-based indicator would be the quality of groundwater, which is affected by the amount of nitrogen applied to the soil. An indicator reflecting the loss of nitrate to groundwater would be effect-based. The means-based evaluation looks at farmers' practices of agriculture, and the effect-based evaluation considers the actual effects of the agricultural system. For example, the means-based analysis might look at pesticides and fertilization methods that farmers are using, and effect-based analysis would consider how much CO₂ is being emitted or what the nitrogen content of the soil is.

The environmental impact of agriculture involves impacts on a variety of different factors: the soil, water, the air, animal and soil variety, people, plants, and the food itself. Agriculture contributes to a number larger of environmental issues that cause environmental degradation including: climate change, deforestation, biodiversity loss, dead zones, genetic engineering, irrigation problems, pollutants, soil degradation, and waste. Because of agriculture's importance to global social and environmental systems, the international community has committed to increasing sustainability of food production as part of Sustainable Development .

Pesticides

The environmental effects of pesticides describe the broad series of consequences of using pesticides. The unintended consequences of pesticides is one of the main drivers of the negative impact of modern industrial agriculture on the environment. Pesticides, because they are toxic chemicals meant to kill pest species, can affect non-target species, such as plants, animals and humans. Over 98% of sprayed insecticides and 95% of herbicides reach a destination other than their target species, because they are sprayed or spread across entire agricultural fields. Other agrochemicals, such as fertilizers, can also have negative effects on the environment.

Plastics

The plastic materials themselves are often and broadly referred to as Plasticulture. It include soil fumigation film, irrigation drip tape/tubing, plastic plant packaging cord, nursery pots and bales, but the term is most often used to describe all kinds of plastic plant/soil coverings. Such coverings range from plastic mulch film, row coverings, high and low tunnels to plastic greenhouses.

Techniques

There are some techniques which are useful in better farming. These are like,

1. Conservation tillage

Conservation tillage is an alternative tillage method for farming which is more sustainable for the soil and surrounding ecosystem. This is done by allowing the residue of the previous harvest's crops to remain in the soil before tilling for the next crop. Conservation tillage has shown to improve many things such as soil moisture retention, and reduce erosion. Some disadvantages are the fact that more expensive equipment is needed for this process, more pesticides will need to be used, and the positive effects take a long time to be visible. The barriers of instantiating a conservation tillage policy are that farmers are reluctant to change their methods, and would protest a more expensive, and time-consuming method of tillage than the conventional one they are used to.

2. Biological pest control

Biological control or bio-control is a method of controlling pests, whether pest animals such as insects and mites, weeds, or pathogens affecting animals or plants by using other organisms. It relies on predation, parasitism, herbivory, or other natural mechanisms, but typically also involves an active human management role. It can be an important component of integrated pest management programmes.

There are three basic strategies for biological control: classical (importation), where a natural enemy of a pest is introduced in the hope of achieving control; inductive (augmentation), in which a large population of natural enemies are administered for quick pest control; and (conservation), in which measures are taken to maintain natural enemies through regular reestablishment.

Natural enemies of insects play an important part in limiting the densities of potential pests. Biological control agents such as these include predators, parasitoids, pathogens, and competitors.

3. Increase in investment

While research has repeatedly shown that the world population is growing at an alarming rate and is soon to outpace the world's current agricultural output in a few decades, there still appears to be a lack of solid

investment in agriculture. This is especially true when you compare other sectors and industries of the economy.

Insufficient attention is given to investing in agriculture — improving farming operations and the lives of those in rural areas. This is an issue that needs to be rectified. Adequate and targeted agricultural investment can result in high yield and other improvements such as increased agriculture infrastructure.

4. Improved storage facilities and infrastructure

Considering that the majority of top agricultural-producing nations are dealing with many other issues highlighted in this article, it makes perfect sense that they also struggle with the lack of efficient storage facilities.

The purpose of agriculture in today's world is to increase food security around the globe. This aim cannot be achieved if farmers have to deal with inefficient storage facilities. It can be said that agricultural produce storage is just as pertinent as farming.

When trying to solve this issue, it is imperative to understand that it must be viewed as a business issue, rather than a farming one. For this reason, there needs to be the creation of ample storage such as cold storage facilities and on-farm storage units. These products can raise the availability of products.

5. Introduction of modern farming technology

Some top agricultural-producing nations, such as Nigeria, Guinea, and India are overwhelmed with a dearth of mechanization in their farming operations. The use of conventional and crude tools instead of machines in the farming process required to feed the world's growing population isn't something that should be allowed to fly.

There is a plethora of benefits associated with introducing mechanized farming. Nevertheless, various measures will need to be put in place for this to happen. Some measures will require forward-thinking government policies, such as subsidizing machine purchases and promoting the re-education of farms on the benefits of improving their agricultural processes with the times. Doing this can result in an increased agricultural produce yield.

6. Increased availability of fertile land

When it comes to farming, one problem farmer's face is land shortage. While millions of hectares are used for agricultural purposes every year, millions more hectares are lost to erosion, Stalinization, desertification, and urbanization. When land lost to urbanization, desertification, erosion, and human habitation are accounted for, the remainder appear to not be sufficient to cater to the world's agricultural demand. This is especially important as the world's population continues to grow. Furthermore, when land is set aside for non-agricultural purposes, it is rarely restored for farming purposes. This is because government policies are formulated to stop the frequent use of lands for non-agricultural purposes.

Farmers' education is vital

This is another solution because it will help farmers understand how to farm properly and use new techniques that will improve their lives. This is vital because they need to know how to manage their land properly, so they receive maximum yields from each crop planted on their land. Having access to information about modern farming techniques also helps them make better decisions about what types of seeds should be purchased for planting in their fields each season.

7. The requirement for Crop Insurance

Farming is a risky business because there are many things which can go wrong during cultivation or harvesting season. Farmers should always consider purchasing crop insurance as it will help them recover from any losses caused by natural disasters or pests like insects, animals, etc. It is important for farmers to have proper knowledge about crop insurance, so they can take advantage of this benefit provided by various companies at affordable rates.

9. Budgeting

When any business is being run, it is important to ensure it is run with a firm budget. This is especially important when running a farm, as the costs can quickly spin out of control over an extended period of time. It also helps that the effect investing in agriculture has is effective and fast. Nevertheless, an extremely suited catalyst required to achieve this growth is finance.

The inability of small-scale farmers to get the loans required to finance their farming activities can result in a cap on their production and efficiency. Proper restructuring of finance options and systems and lower interest rates linked to loans can help agriculture and small-scale farmers have a brighter future. Farmers might also want to enlist the services of a trained accountant. This trained accountant can handle the farming budget to ensure it doesn't spiral out of control.

In addition to that, it's essential to promote sustainable and ethical agricultural practices, such as:

1. Organic farming
2. Agro-ecology
3. Regenerative agriculture
4. Fair trade and labour practices
5. Environmental conservation and restoration

By prioritizing ethical agriculture, we can protect human health, well-being, and the environment, while promoting a more just and sustainable food system.

Unethical practices in agriculture can have far-reaching consequences for human health, psychology, and the environment. Some of the specific ways in which unethical agriculture affects humans and their psychology.

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